

Deliverable:
D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.
Final Data management plan
Workpackage 1 of OH-
Harmony-Cap: Project
Coordination

Responsible Partner: P13-SSI

Contributing partners: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA.

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1: Data Management Plan		
Project Acronym	OH-Harmony-Cap		
Author	Nadia Boisen and Flemming Scheutz		
Other contributors			
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Type	R, DEC, other		
<i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	Save date: 14-Dec-22		
Dissemination level	PU		
<i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination	<i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i> OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):		

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Background

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project, **Integrative Action-2.2, OH-HARMONY-CAP**: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants

<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

OH-HARMONY-CAP (One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants) is a 3-year project that aims to: 1. Collect information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe by developing an in-depth OHLabCap survey. 2. Examine current and best practices within the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. 3. Produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of pathogens.

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Data Management Plan (DMP) is an important element of data management during a project as it is needed to continuously tracking, monitoring, analyseing and storing data in order to ensure progress throughout the project. Note, OH-Harmony-Cap is dedicated to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR-principle). Further, this data asset will be readily available for all our purposes, as well as those that may need this data in the future, also contributing to the sustainability of the project and its outcomes.

This is the final data management plan

Process and format

The list of data covered in OH-Harmony-Cap DMP has been specified and updated the project and the management of the data is discussed proactively and the DMP was regularly discussed with the WP-leaders and with the OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium during the project.

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

First version of DMP (2020)

26 datasets are listed in the final version of OH-HARMONY-CAP DMP:

The screenshot displays the 'View OH-HARMONY CAP - Data Management' interface. It features a sidebar on the left with navigation options: Home, CDP, Hub dashboard, Pinned views, OH-HARMONY CAP Data Management, Last Open, OHEJP, and Manage hubs. The main content area shows a table of datasets with the following columns: Dataset ID, Category, Type of data, Species, Matrix, Description of d..., Contact, Dissemination, and Sustainability. The table lists 26 datasets, including JIP-4-2_WP2OHL, JIP-4-WP3_ONE_H, JIP-4-WP4_HARM, and JIP-4-WP4_SHIGE. Each row includes a checkbox, a link icon, an information icon, and a comment icon. The interface also shows a 'Views overview' section at the top and a pagination control at the bottom indicating 'Page 1 of 1' and 'View 1 - 26 of 26'.

Dataset ID	Category	Type of data	Species	Matrix	Description of d...	Contact	Dissemination	Sustainability
JIP-4-2_WP2OHL...	Research data	Questionnaires	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Human;F...	Results of pilots...	Flemming Scheut...	The final result wi...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP3_ONE_H...	Research data	Questionnaires	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Food;wat...	Establishing curre...	Declan Bolton, D...	The four questio...	31 Dec 2023
JIP-4-WP4_HARM...	Research data	Data collection	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Human;F...	Collection of the l...	Rosangela Tozzoli...	The result of the ...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP4_HARM...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Food;wat...	Evaluation, select...	Karin Troell, karin...	The results will b...	31 Mar 2021
JIP-4-2.2.OH-HAR...	Research data	Questionnaires	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Human;F...	Pilot survey cond...	Nadia Boisen nbo...	The pilot survey ...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP2OHLAB...	Research data	Questionnaires	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Human;F...	OHLabCap: 59 qu...	Nadia Boisen nbo...	The OHLabCap su...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP2-T5_DEV...	Research data	Questionnaires	Bacterial species;...	Food	Food business su...	Nadia Boisen nbo...	The survey will be...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP2.OH-HA...	Research data	Data collection	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Human;F...	Result of the OHL...	Flemming Scheut...	The answers fro...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP2-T4-RES...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Human;w...	Result of a 56 qu...	Flemming Scheut...	The gathered info...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP2_OHLAB...	Research data	Questionnaires	Bacterial species;...	Not relevant	A letter of invitat...	Flemming scheut...	The letter of invit...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OHHARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;water;Foo...	A report on the pl...	Flemming Scheut...	This report will b...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OHHARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Food	Report on the sur...	Catarina Flink, Ca...	This technical rep...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OG-HARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;water;Hu...	Technical report ...	Declan Bolton De...	The report will be...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;water;Food	Technical report ...	Declan Bolton De...	The report will be...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;water;Foo...	Technical report ...	Declan Bolton De...		31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Human;w...	Result of four qu...	Declan Bolton De...	The result of the ...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Research data	Data collection	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Food;Fae...	a final report on r...	Rosangela Tpzzi...	The report will be...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-2-WP2-OH-H...	Methodologies	Methods	Bacterial species	Animal;Faeces;Bl...	Updated and exp...	Flemming Scheut...		31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-WP4_STEC_E...	Methodologies	Methods	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Blood;Fae...	More than 865 di...	Flemming Scheut...	manuscript in pre...	1 Jan 2024
JIP-4-WP4_SHIGE...	Methodologies	Methods	Emerging pathog...	Diverse;Faeces;Bl...	PCR method: Pro...	Flemming Scheut...	manuscript in pre...	1 Jan 2024
JIP-4-WP4_STEC_E...	Methodologies	Methods	Zoonotic bacteria...	Animal;Blood;Fae...	More than 865 di...	Flemming Scheut...	manuscript in pre...	1 Jan 2024
JIP-4-WP4_SHIGE...	Methodologies	Methods	Emerging pathog...	Diverse;Faeces;Bl...	PCR method: Pro...	Flemming Scheut...	manuscript in pre...	1 Jan 2024
JIP-4-WP4_TRANL...	Methodologies	Methods		Diverse	Training program...	Tosini Fabio fablo...		31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Methodologies	Methods	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Food;Hu...	A list of collecte...	Tozzoli Rosangela...	The list of protoc...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Methodologies	Methods	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Human;w...	Ranking and eval...	Tozzoli Rosangela...	The ranking and c...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Methodologies	Methods	Bacterial species;...	Animal;Human;F...	Harmonised labo...	Tozzoli Rosangela...	The protocols will...	31 Dec 2022
JIP-4-OH-HARMO...	Methodologies	Methods	Bacterial species;...	Animal;water;Hu...	a list of reference...	Tozzoli Rosangela...	The reference ma...	31 Dec 2022